

LEGAL REGULATION OF THE ACTIVITY OF INSPECTORS-PSYCHOLOGISTS ON JUVENILE CASES IN THE SYSTEM OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15464171>

Annotation. In the article legal and organizational bases of activity of inspectors-psychologists on minors' affairs in bodies of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan are considered. The tasks, functions, documentary support, criteria of effectiveness, forms of interaction with educational organizations and other subjects of prevention are analyzed. The system of indicators of work efficiency, normative base and recommendations on improvement of service of inspectors-psychologists are given.

Key words: inspector-psychologist, minors, prevention of delinquency, internal affairs bodies, social work, accounting, performance indicators, regulatory and legal framework.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются правовые и организационные основы деятельности инспекторов-психологов по делам несовершеннолетних в органах внутренних дел Республики Узбекистан. Проанализированы задачи, функции, документальное сопровождение, критерии эффективности, формы взаимодействия с образовательными организациями и другими субъектами профилактики. Приводится система индикаторов результативности работы, нормативная база и даны рекомендации по совершенствованию службы инспекторов-психологов.

Ключевые слова: инспектор-психолог, несовершеннолетние, профилактика правонарушений, органы внутренних дел, социальная работа, учет, индикаторы эффективности, нормативно-правовая база.

The increase in the crime rate, recorded in official statistics, causes justified concern in society and raises the question of the need to strengthen preventive measures, especially in work with minors. In the context of such dynamics, it is necessary to build an effective system of preventive action based on interagency cooperation and involvement of qualified specialists.

Under article 4 of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan On Prevention of Child Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency of 29 September 2010, «the main objectives of the prevention of neglect and juvenile delinquency among minors are: to prevent neglect and homelessness among minors and their committing delinquency or other antisocial acts, to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to such behaviour; to ensure the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of minors; to promote law-abiding behaviour among minors; the socio-pedagogical rehabilitation of minors and families in socially dangerous situations; and the identification and suppression of cases involving the enticement of minors into committing offenses or other antisocial actions».

In order to accomplish the above-mentioned tasks, the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter - IAB), in accordance with the law , carry out their activities in the following main areas:

Firstly, the identification and prevention of neglect and juvenile delinquency among minors. IAB carry out raids to identify neglected children in the streets, train stations, basements and other places where they congregate; refer street children to rehabilitation centers; work to identify their parents or guardians and hold them accountable for improper upbringing, etc., because “neglected children and adolescents left without adult supervision are at increased risk of criminalization, which requires targeted programs for early identification and support” .

Secondly, individual preventive work. A special role in the mechanism of prevention of juvenile delinquency is assigned to individual work with minors, aimed at preventing them from committing offenses and antisocial acts, as well as at minimizing the negative factors that entail socially dangerous activity of a teenager. Thus, IAB keep records of and work with minors on the preventive register or who are considered at risk. Within this activity, officers of the prevention units: conduct preventive conversations with minors and their parents (or guardians); monitor their observance of the study and leisure time regimes; carry out regular inspections of families where violations of children’s rights (violence, lack of proper supervision, criminogenic situation) are possible. Currently, the electronic system “E-Voyaga yetmagan” has been fully implemented at the national level, enabling the registration and monitoring of unsupervised and unattended minors.

Thirdly, work with dysfunctional families. Preventive work with the family, as noted by G.Y. Karimova, “is an important activity on the right path to the formation of a minor’s personality. It is through his relatives that a teenager learns what is good and what is bad. Therefore, the main direction of prevention carried out by the bodies of the system for the prevention of neglect and delinquency is close contact with families where underage children grow up or which have a negative impact on their development and upbringing”. IAB officers cooperate with social protection and education agencies, conducting raids and inspections of families where violations of the rights of minors may occur. Based on the revealed facts, IAB officers can: issue a warning to parents; bring parents to administrative responsibility; prepare materials for submission to the court for deprivation of parental rights.

Fourthly, cooperation with bodies and institutions involved in the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency, including: commissions on children’s issues; education authorities and educational institutions; guardianship and trusteeship bodies; healthcare authorities and medical institutions; labor and social protection bodies; NGOs and international structures, etc. work with educational institutions. According to I. V. Fedorova, S.V.Kalinina: “In the long term, the implementation of general preventive measures by the police in cooperation with other bodies authorized to carry out these activities, as much as possible prevents the possibility of situations in which minors find themselves homeless or neglected, when there is a situation in which they may commit an offense or crime» . Uzbekistan’s internal affairs bodies actively cooperate with educational institutions by: conducting preventive talks with pupils on the consequences of offenses; monitoring compliance with discipline in schools; and responding to reports of violence and bullying among pupils.

Fifthly, rehabilitation and social adaptation of offenders. Measures of social rehabilitation and social adaptation are applied, in accordance with the procedure established by law, to persons who have suffered from offenses, as well as to persons inclined to commit offenses or who have already committed them, by the relevant specialized services directly involved in the prevention of offenses. According to part 2 of Art. 14 of the Code Administrative Liability of the Republic of Uzbekistan, if minors commit administrative offences under articles 61, 1161, 1162, 1163, 125, 1251, 126, 127, 128, 1281, 1282, 1283, 1284, 1285, 1286, 129, 130, 131, 132, 133, 134, 135, 1351, 136, 138, 183, 185, 1851, 1852, 1853, 194, 1941, 1961, 2061, 2091, 218, 220, 221 of this Code, they are subject to administrative liability on general grounds. Taking into account the nature of the offense committed and the personality of the offender, cases against these persons (except for persons who have committed offenses under Articles 194, 1941 and 1961 of this Code) may be transferred, and those who have committed offenses under Articles 61, 2061 of this Code shall be referred to district (city) commissions on children's issues, where the following educational measures shall be applied to them on the basis of the law: submit a submission to the district (city) court on the imposition on the child of the following educational measures: submit a proposal to the district (city) court on the imposition on the child of the following obligations; issuing a warning to the parents or guardians of the child; placing the child under the supervision of their parents or substitute guardians, or state caregivers, and with their consent — under the supervision of a labor collective or a non-governmental nonprofit organization; applying to the district (city) court with a request to impose on a child who has reached the age of fifteen the obligation to compensate for or eliminate the material damage caused, if the child is an independent worker and the amount of damage does not exceed the established basic calculation amount, or to impose on the child the obligation to compensate for material damage, not exceeding the established basic calculation amount, through their labor. Children who have reached the age of 16 and are engaged in self-employment are fined in the cases and in the amounts provided for in the Code of Administrative Liability. In addition, they have the right to apply to the courts for the child to be sent to educational establishments of the country in the cases and according to the procedure provided for by legislative acts.

The basic role in the system of prevention of juvenile delinquency is played by a specially introduced position - Inspector-psychologist for juvenile issues (hereinafter - Inspector-psychologist), whose activities are focused on the early identification of risks, patronization of families and formation of stable legal attitudes among adolescents.

The inspector-psychologists' service is being formed as the most important link in the preventive activities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs within the framework of the nationwide prevention system. Their work covers not only behavioral deviations of adolescents, but also contributes to the improvement of the educational environment, prevention of domestic violence, family dysfunction and the formation of a legal culture among the younger generation.

In order to meet the "objectives of improving the psychological environment in general secondary education establishments by working with each pupil, fostering an irreconcilable attitude to juvenile delinquency among minors, and targeting problem pupils directly at their places of residence with the involvement of their parents". In accordance with Presidential Decision No. PP-5050 of 02.04.2021 "On additional organizational measures for further

improving the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime” , the position of “inspector-psychologist for minors” was introduced in the structures of the district and municipal internal affairs bodies, with a staff complement of 2,000.

According to the Decree of the Head of State of February 5, 2024, the positions of inspector-psychologists (senior inspector-psychologists) from the internal affairs bodies for minors were transferred to the structure of the National Guard. The National Guard has established a department for work with children and its territorial subdivisions, as well as the positions of senior inspector-psychologists and inspector-psychologists for minors.

On March 18, 2025, a meeting was held in the Office of the General Procurator, chaired by Presidential Adviser D. Kadyrov, at which it was announced that the positions of National Guard juvenile affairs inspectors and psychologists and 2,000 staff units had been transferred to the Ministry of Internal Affairs. In this connection, specific tasks have been set for the internal affairs bodies to work with minors based on the principle of “family - makhalla - school”.

Today, according to the current regulations of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the main tasks of juvenile affairs inspectors and psychologists include:

- organizing systematic work with pupils prone to committing crimes or aspiring to negative leadership within the framework of the principle “Family - Mahalla - School” together with psychologists of educational institutions and prevention inspectors in the makhallas;
- Participation in morning rulings in schools to explain to pupils and teachers the negative consequences of delinquency and the importance of observing school discipline;
- organization of information exchange with the school psychologist and teaching staff regarding pupils under “internal control” and identification of negative changes in the behavior of other pupils;
- launching mechanisms of targeted preventive and psychological work aimed at forming legal immunity among schoolchildren against delinquency and deviant behavior;
- Implementation of targeted programs to improve the moral and psychological atmosphere in schools;
- Conducting awareness-raising and legal education activities with pupils and their parents on the causes and consequences of juvenile delinquency and the prevention of possible road traffic accidents involving pupils;
- Organization of activities in schools to identify and eliminate factors contributing to uncontrolled behavior among pupils;
- organizing “Pupil” activities in Internet clubs and other entertainment venues near schools in order to prevent pupils from being uncontrolled during the educational process;
- assistance in early detection and prevention of negative manifestations, vagrancy and begging among pupils through the formation of a sense of patriotism and devotion to the Motherland;
- jointly with the chairmen of makhalla assemblies of citizens, organizing regular checks of school attendance, identifying pupils who miss classes without a valid reason, and eliminating factors preventing minors from receiving education, together with the competent institutions;

- all-round assistance to students' leisure time, professional orientation, development of their physical and creative abilities, with special attention to students with difficult upbringing;

- Based on the results of a study of the living conditions of problem pupils, a report is drawn up for inclusion in the social and preventive register;

- If neglected and abandoned children under 3 years of age are identified, assisting in their transfer to infant homes in cooperation with the guardianship and custody and health care authorities;

- Strengthening cooperation with the guardianship and custody authorities, especially with regard to the admission to the Centers for Social and Legal Assistance of minors who have suffered abuse in dysfunctional families or by parents who abuse alcohol;

- Participation in court proceedings on the restriction, deprivation and restoration of parental rights;

- Notifying the Children's Ombudsman and submitting the relevant documents to the interdepartmental commission on minors' affairs in cases of parents' or legal representatives' evasion of their obligations to provide for, raise and educate a child, as well as in cases where a negative influence on the minor's behavior or cruel treatment of the minor is detected;

- Participation in meetings of district and city National Commissions on Children's Affairs and in discussions in the relevant organizations and departments on every crime committed by minors;

- Participation in the organization and conduct of discussions on crimes committed by students of the educational institution assigned to them, etc.

In addition, in order to ensure that minors are brought up in a healthy family environment and to prevent antisocial behavior such as vagrancy and begging, as well as the abandonment of children without parental care, the following social prevention activities are organized in cooperation with other responsible structures:

- assistance in employment of unemployed family members;
- assistance in obtaining soft loans and subsidies;
- assistance in joining craftsmen's associations;
- involvement in paid public works;
- assistance in allocation of land plots for farming;
- assistance in organizing activities in livestock breeding and other areas;
- referrals to mono-centers for training to learn a trade;
- involvement in entrepreneurial activities;
- referral to compulsory medical treatment;
- reconciliation of conflict families and families on the verge of divorce, etc.

In carrying out the tasks assigned to juvenile affairs units, cooperation is carried out with specialized services of internal affairs bodies, other law enforcement agencies, governmental and non-governmental organizations in accordance with legislative acts.

The criteria by which the performance of inspectors-psychologists working with minors is assessed include the following indicators:

- Reducing the number of students under internal control in educational institutions;
- Reducing the level of various asocial manifestations and juvenile delinquency;
- Reducing the number of minors from socially dangerous environments and those prone to antisocial behavior involved in extracurricular and community activities;

- Reducing the suicide rate among minors;
- Increase in the number of students covered by organized forms of summer health improvement, leisure and employment.

At the same time, the current legislation allows the establishment of additional quantitative and qualitative indicators reflecting the specificity and effectiveness of the professional activity of the inspector-psychologist.

In Uzbekistan, according to statistical data for 2024, measures have been taken in the mahallas for the early prevention of juvenile delinquency and the meaningful organization of their leisure time: 104,139 children left unattended in public places have been identified in order to prevent neglect among minors, of whom 1,715 children have been placed in social and legal assistance centers, 34 children have been placed in educational institutions, 789 children left without parental care have been appointed guardians and trustees; 778 parents with a negative influence on the upbringing of their children have been employed, and 6,828 have been involved in optional circles; With a view to the early prevention of delinquency among students, some 180 prevention inspectors (30 of them for women) have been set up in 212 higher education institutions; some 180 "Qalqon" groups have been set up in higher education institutions, in which 2,456 students have been involved on a voluntary basis; 5,920 minors were returned to their studies, 8,136 were involved in sports, 1,416 in small businesses and 2,719 were placed in Barkamol Avlod centers; 25,331 minors were discussed in the mahalla, 267 were sent for compulsory treatment and 14,648 were removed from the prevention register.

Thus, the institutionalization of the service of juvenile affairs inspectors and psychologists in the structure of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an important stage in the formation of a modern model of prevention among juveniles. Given the growth of juvenile delinquency and the increasing requirements for interagency cooperation, the activities of the inspector-psychologist should be viewed not only as administrative and controlling, but above all as a social-preventive and corrective-psychological function.

Scientific analysis allows us to assert that the effectiveness of this service is largely determined by the degree of normative regulation, the level of professional training, the integration of digital tools and international standards into the practice of work. In this regard, it seems reasonable to implement the following directions for improving the institute of inspectors-psychologists:

- approval of a unified professional standard and job description. In the absence of a clearly defined professional standard for the position of inspector-psychologist, there are significant discrepancies in the practice of performing functional duties in different regions. This leads to fragmented approaches, different levels of quality of preventive care, and, in some cases, to legal conflicts. The development of a unified professional standard will ensure: legal certainty and transparency of competencies, functions and powers of a specialist; unified qualification requirements for education, experience and skills; compliance with the principle of legal certainty in personnel and attestation policy. The introduction of a job description based on the standard will allow structuring the daily activities of the inspector, increase his accountability and reduce management risks.

- systematic retraining and certification at least once every two years. The prevention of juvenile delinquency requires constant updating of knowledge in the field of psychology, pedagogy, juvenile justice, digital security and conflictology. In accordance with international

practice (in particular, the experience of Germany, France and South Korea) , staff working with children undergo regular professional verification of competencies. Periodic retraining and certification: contributes to the updating of professional knowledge taking into account changes in legislation and social trends; ensures a unified standard for the quality of assistance provided; allows to identify and eliminate professional deficits at an early stage; contributes to the formation of a sustainable professional core of the service.

-introduction of digital mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation of performance. In the modern context, it is critically important to ensure prompt, reliable, and systematic assessment of the effectiveness of inspectors' work. The introduction of digital platforms and electronic monitoring logs will make it possible to: automate the collection and analysis of key indicators (work with families, number of detected violations, coverage of preventive measures, etc.); ensure the transparency and validity of management decisions; promptly identify weak links and risk points; create a basis for analytical and scientific data processing. Moreover, the digitalization of prevention records is fully in line with the strategic objectives of civil service reform and digital governance set out in the national strategy "Uzbekistan 2030".

-expanding the format of cooperation with non-governmental organizations and international structures specializing in the protection of children's rights. International experience shows that sustainable results in the prevention of juvenile delinquency are achieved with the active participation of civil society. Cooperation with non-governmental organizations and international structures allows: to adapt advanced methods of working with adolescents in difficult life situations; to introduce restorative practices and elements of mediation technologies; to improve the legal and psychological literacy of children and parents; to conduct joint scientific and practical research and projects in the field of juvenile prevention. The institutionalization of such interaction can be enshrined in interagency agreements and included in the system of performance indicators for the activities of inspectors-psychologists.

Thus, the implementation of the proposed measures will strengthen the role of the inspector-psychologist as a key actor in the system of state support and legal protection of minors, thereby ensuring a sustainable reduction in juvenile delinquency and an increase in social stability.

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